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Evaluating and Insuring Cyber Risks within Organizations

PhD in Mathematics and Applications for Social Sciences

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President of the jury

- **Pr. Werner**, INRIA & Ecole Polytechnique Paris

Examiners

- **Dr. Bazalgette** Innovation Expert for Artificial Intelligence at Defence Innovation Agency
- **Pr. Fass**, LORIA/INRIA
- **Dr. Pastorelli**, University Côte d'Azur

Members of the Jury

- **Dr. Cruck**, Ministry of Armed Forces
- **Pr. Godé**, Aix-Marseille University
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